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Research Article

**MORBIDITY OF MALARIA IN PROVINCE OF PUNJAB &
DISTRIBUION OF THE SPECIES OF PLASMODIUM**¹Dr Ghulam Raza, ¹Dr Dost Ali.¹DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this research work is to investigate the frequency of parasites and species of Malaria in Punjab, Pakistan's province.

Methodology: This was an observational study which carried out in all districts of Punjab in the duration of complete five years from January 2014 to December 2018. It relates to observation of Malaria Control Program (MCP) in Punjab when microscopists of all districts saw blood samples of men and women of all age groups, affected with fever. Highly professional Microscopists again examined the slides showing positive results. Data of all examined slides from all districts of Punjab sent to Lahore for collection and further examination on monthly basis.

Results: During the period of the study, screening of 5.840 million slides showed the prevalence of malarial parasite in 0.160 million approximately which produced 4.460 BER (blood examination rate), 2.940 SPR (Slide Positivity Rate), 41.0% FR (Falciparum Ratio), and 1.360 API (Annual Parasite Incidences). The examination of the remaining cases carried out after the season of monsoon.

Conclusion: Markers of malaria were more than that were expected. The problem can be minimizing by efficient management / role of RBM (Roll Back Malaria) programs. So there is requirement of incorporated method for identification, cure and avoidance from this disease.

Key Words: Blood Examination Rate, Malaria Control Program, Slide Positivity Rate, Plasmodium Vivax, Falciparum, Occurrence, Morbidity.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ghulam Raza,**

DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan.

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INTRODUCTION:

Malaria is among the universal problems of health and weighs down the health in world's underdeveloped countries. Almost 50% of inhabitants of world are available with high danger of Malaria in which about 250 million are medical cases. In 2006, there was occurrence of one million deaths due to malaria [1]. There is also great impact of this widespread disease on our country, Pakistan. At present, Pakistan is among those countries which are the victims of this disease with low rate of occurrence. It is 2nd most frequently reported disease by public sector organizations [2]. There is a broad distribution of malaria causing parasites which are *P. Vivax* & *P. Falciparum*.

The most common species are *A. culicifacies* & *A. stephensi* [3]. There are different major impacts of this disease on the health of children [4] particularly suffering from malnourishment [5]. The after effects of this disease are that it leave weakness in the body which can cause other infections and slow down the process of development. Indeed, non-fatal cases can have harsh after effects. Females with pregnancy [5] have high risk of acquisition of this complication, which can cause the death of the baby or low weight at the time of birth. If it is delay or no cure of this disease in time, it can cause the death of the patient. Malaria has an association with the social & economic conditions [6]. The treatment of this disease is very expensive for both patients as well as health care facilities. There is also impact of level of education on the prevalence of this disease. The reason of this study was to analyze the symptoms of this disease and see the disbursement of species of plasmodium throughout the observational period of 2014-2018 in Punjab, Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY:

MCP started in all health care centers in different districts of Punjab. The samples of blood had taken from all men and women of all age groups having fever because of malaria. The samples of blood made by tagging and marking of slides with the help of Giemsa's Stain and catechized by skilled Microscopists to check the existence of plasmodium and to differentiate the types of its species. Administrators and leading microscopists observed the work of health workers and microscopists, reliability of prepared slides and cases having positive results. These senior supervisors made an examination of slides having positive results and after that they also made a random analysis of cases having negative results.

The obtained data noted and recorded in accordance with months and districts in Lahore. The calculations of Blood Examination Rate (BER =total slides x 100/population), Slide Positivity Rate (SPR=no. of positive slides x 100/total no. of slides), species differentiation and Falciparum Ratio (FR%=total falciparum x 100/total no. of positive slides) and Annual Parasite Incidence (API =total positive cases x 100 /population) carried out. These prepared reports had made public and again re-collected from Provisional Malarial Directorate for further examination and research.

RESULTS:

In the duration of 5 years (2014-2018), the analysis of 5,843,626 slides carried out by MCP in all over Punjab. According to this research 165,177 cases were suffering from malaria. *P. Vivax* was present in 97,405 cases and *P. Falciparum* was present in 67,772 cases as given in Table-1.

Table-I: Five Year Table with Plasmodium Species

Years	Slides Tested	Positive for Malaria	<i>P. Vivax</i>	<i>P. Falciparum</i>
2014	731038.0	23218.0	12938.0	10280.0
2015	902223.0	38629.0	20718.0	17911.0
2016	1519648.0	40614.0	27235.0	13379.0
2017	1313794.0	28107.0	17463.0	10644.0
2018	1376923.0	34609.0	19051.0	15558.0
Total	5843626.0	165177.0	97405.0	67772.0

In accordance with the total number of analyzed slides and number of cases showing positive results, the analyzed data for BER, SPR, FR% & API is given in Table-2.

Table-II: Comparison of Five Years Parameters

Years	*BER	**SPR	***FR	****API
2014	4.870	3.170	44.00%	1.540
2015	5.750	4.230	47.00%	2.440
2016	4.220	2.670	33.00%	1.120
2017	3.640	2.120	37.00%	0.770
2018	3.820	2.510	45.00%	0.960
Average	4.460	2.940	41.00%	1.360

*BER : Blood examination rate

**SPR : Slide positivity rate

***FR : Falciparum ratio

****API : Annual parasite incidence

During these years Blood Examination Rate was 4.870, 5.750, 4.220, 3.640 & 3.820 in 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018 correspondingly having an average of 4.460. Rate of Slide Positivity during these years was 3.170, 4.230, 2.670, 2.120 and 2.150 correspondingly having an average of 2.940. The average ratio of Falciparum was 41.0%. During this period API was 0.770 to 2.440 having an average of 1.360. The monthly data of Punjab shows that SPR, FR%, API is greater than before, in the season of monsoon.

DISCUSSION:

Pakistan is amongst those countries which have moderate occurrences of malaria. The occurrence of this disease differs from one place to another. According to the report of MCP [2], the cases showing positive results from Punjab were 30% of the country. In the duration of given 5 years, MCP had seen almost 5.840 slides from all districts of Punjab. Among these, 0.160 million slides were having positive results for malaria. BER varied its value during the given period from 3.640 to 4.870 but

in 2015 its rate was 5.750 which was higher than its optimum level [7] which is 5. SPR had an average of 2.94 but the optimum level of SPR is 2. On the other hand, API had an average of 1.360 but the optimum level of API is less than 0.50. It seemed that both indicators had higher value than the optimum level. In 1997, in Punjab the slide positivity rate was 2.40 while it was 2.70 in the country [8]. From 1999 to 2001 it raised to 3.1 [9], sometimes it reached [10] up to 5.90. slide positivity rate shows the frequency and annual parasite incidences shows occurrence of malaria in any locality. The appropriate level of FR [7, 11] is not more than 40%. While in 2014, 2015, 2018 its value was 44 percent, 47 percent and 45 percent accordingly but in 2016 & 2017 its value was 33.0% and 37.0% accordingly. FR%, API & slide positivity rate start increasing from the season of monsoon and ends up to the month of January. After 80s Falciparum has become dominant while before 80s Vivax was on higher rate [9, 12]. In the same way, resistance increased against the Chloroquine [13, 14].

In the above mentioned research duration FR% was close to optimum level but according to the data of 1991 and 2001 [9] its rate increased than the optimum level, resulting complexities. Resistance against drugs also caused an increase in complications. According to this research, in Punjab the situation was favorable for the higher rate of malarial infection. Pakistan aimed to reduce the cases of malaria through cure by attaining RBM and MDGs (Millennium Development Goals) [15]. Light Microscope used to reduce cost. An easy and non-expensive test, RPD (Rapid Diagnostic Test [16] used. But it is difficult to use these techniques in distant localities. WHO advised a safe and effective cure of malaria. WHO [2, 17] discouraged the use of immunotherapy. They advised chloroquine and primaquine for *P. vivax* infection. Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine & Artesunate used in a combine therapy against non-fatal falciparum malaria. In case of complex Falciparum cure starts from injection of quinine and further patient needs to get admission in hospital. It is not vital to utilize Chloroquine [2].

It is very important to take proper measures for prevention against this fatal disease. Method of roll back malaria is far away from international aims to decrease this complications in the whole world due to poor infrastructure of the health care facilities, low level of education, poorness, less amount of doctors in non-urban areas with unskilled staff and adverse monitoring, causing the high morbidity due to the epidemic of malaria. MCP is ambitious to achieve goals by tackling the problems, they have to face. In this regard, they are in a need of a corporation from the higher concerning authorities, who can show their contribution by providing funds and other facilities and proper education to overcome this disease.

CONCLUSION:

All essential identifiers of malaria are more than the reasonable level in Punjab. The prevalence of malaria is at higher rate after the season of monsoon. The worldwide project of RBM approaches needs to give preference and to implement also. An incorporated method of identification and cure of malaria, in accordance with the use of anti-malarial drugs, is now most essential for minimizing the symptoms and death rate due to malaria.

REFERENCES:

1. Caulfield LE, Richard SA, Black RE. Undernutrition as an underlying cause of Malaria morbidity and mortality in children less than five years old. *AM J Trop Med Hyg* 2004;71(2 suppl):55-63.
2. Jones COH, Williams HA. The social burden of Malaria: what are we measuring? *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 2004;71(2 suppl):156-161.
3. National Malaria Control Program-2007. Directorate of Malaria Control, Ministry of Health, Pakistan.
4. National Malaria Control Program-1997. Directorate of Malaria Control, Ministry of Health, Pakistan.
5. Murtaza G, Memon IA, Noorani AK. Malaria prevalence in Sindh. *Medical Channel* 2004;10(2):41-42.
6. Khan SA, Anwar M, Hussain S, Qureshi AH, Ahmed M, Afzal S. Comparison of optimal Malaria test with light microscopy for the diagnosis of Malaria. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2004;54(8):404-7.
7. Hozhabri S, Akhtar S, Rahbar MH, Luby SP. Prevalence of Plasmodium slide positivity among the children treated for Malaria, Jhangara, Sindh *J Pak Med Assoc* 2000;50(12):401-405.
8. National treatment Guidelines for Malaria, 2005, Directorate of Malaria control, Ministry of Health, Pakistan.
9. Millennium Declaration. New York, United Nation; 2000. Available at <http://www.un.org/millennium/declaration>.
10. The Pakistan National Health Management Information System (HMIS) report 2006. Ministry of Health. Government of Pakistan.
11. World Malaria Report 2008. WHO, Geneva, Switzerland.
12. WHO, EMRO-Roll Back Malaria – Website www.emro.who.int/rbm.
13. Rafi S, Memon MA, Rao MH, Billoo AG. A change of Plasmodium species infecting children in Karachi Over the last decade. *J Pak Med Assoc* 1994;44(7):162-4.
14. Malaria case management Desk guide for clinicians and health care providers, 2007, Directorate of Malaria control, Ministry of health. Government of Pakistan.
15. Khan MA, Smego RA, Razi ST, Beg A. Emerging drugresistance and guidelines for treatment of Malaria. *J Coll Physician Surg Pak* 2005;14(5):319-24.
16. Bryce J, Boschi-pinto C, Shibuya K, Black RE. WHO estimates of the causes of death in children. WHO Child Health Epidemiology Reference Group. *Lancet* 2005;365(9465):1147-52.
17. Murtaza G, Memon IA. Antimalarial Drugs in plasmodium falciparum malaria. *J Coll Physician Surg Pak* 2000;10(12):484-88.